

Supplementary Material: Complete List of Competency Questions for the Conference Paper "Danash et al. Towards Interoperable Digital Product Passports for Furniture Circularity: Ontology Requirements Specification and Gap Analysis"

CQ1 — What are the structural and material characteristics defined for a furniture product model, including dimensions, component list, material composition, and design type?

CQ2 — What is the repairability profile of a furniture product model, including repairability score, disassembly instructions, modularity level, and spare parts availability?

CQ3 — What historical performance data exists for all product instances of a given furniture model?

CQ4 — What are the defined selection criteria for a furniture product model to be suitable for rental, including lead time, spare part availability, modularity, and circularity indicators?

CQ5 — What is the current lifecycle status of a furniture product model, and has it been flagged for discontinuation from the rental portfolio?

CQ6 — What structured product information is available to describe a furniture product instance offered for rental, including physical characteristics, condition state, and circular credentials?

CQ7 — Who published the product information in this DPP, when was it last updated, and has it been verified by a third party?

CQ8 — What usage events have been recorded for a furniture product instance, including rental periods, custody transfers, transport events, and total usage duration?

CQ9 — What damage records exist for a furniture product instance, including damage type, severity, location on the product, and date of occurrence?

CQ10 — What is the current condition state of a returned furniture product instance, and which circular pathway does it qualify for based on defined decision criteria?

CQ11 — Has a furniture product instance undergone aesthetic degradation that would affect its reuse grading or require refurbishment, and what is the resulting product identity after intervention?

CQ12 — What are the structural and material characteristics defined for a furniture product model, including dimensions, component list, material composition, design type, functions, and price?

CQ13 — What environmental impact indicators are declared for a furniture product model across its lifecycle, including carbon footprint, recycled content ratio, and material footprint?

CQ14 — What is the recorded usage of a furniture product model, expressed as number of rental cycles completed and total usage duration across all product instances?

CQ15 — What is the current condition state and intervention history of a furniture product instance offered as used or refurbished, including previous repairs, refurbishments, and number of prior rental cycles?

CQ16 — What functional and spatial characteristics are declared for a furniture product model relevant to consumer suitability assessment, including dimensions, ergonomic properties, and compatibility indicators?

CQ17 — What acquisition cost components are declared for a furniture product instance, including purchase price for new and used conditions and indicative rental pricing structure?

CQ18 — What damage types and severity levels have been recorded across all product instances of a given furniture model, and at which components do they most frequently occur?

CQ19 — Which components of a furniture product model have been most frequently repaired or replaced, and what is the associated repair effort per intervention?

CQ20 — What is the actual number of use cycles and total usage duration recorded for product instances, and how does this compare to the declared expected lifetime?

CQ21 — What disassembly time and effort data has been recorded during repair and refurbishment interventions, attributed to specific components and joints?

CQ22 — What disassembly instructions are published for a furniture product model, specifying the sequence of steps, required tools, joint types, and component accessibility levels?

CQ23 — What spare parts are declared as available for a furniture product model, including part identifiers, compatibility with product versions, and current availability status?

CQ24 — What repair instructions and required skill levels are published for a furniture product model, specifying intervention type, component addressed, and minimum technician qualification?